

CYBERLENINKA

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Tukhtakhodjaeva Z.T

WORD FORMATION MEANS AS THE MANIFESTATION OF THE LAW

OF ECONOMY IN MODERN ENGLISH MASS MEDIA

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Impact Factor

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